

Thermodynamic and Spectroscopic Study of 6-Methyluracil

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The vapour pressure of 6-methyluracil was measured in the temperature range 426-503K by the torsion effusion technique and pressure-temperature equation: $\lg P(\text{kPa}) = 12.09 \pm 0.07 - (6652 \pm 34)/T$ was determined. The sublimation enthalpy $\Delta H_{\text{sub}}^{\circ} = 131 \pm 7 \text{ kJ/mol}$ was derived as mean of the results obtained by the second and third law treatment of the experimental vapour pressure data. The spectroscopic measurements of an infrared investigation on gaseous 6-methyluracil were employed in the thermodynamic functions calculations.

THE biological importance of uracil and its derivatives has prompted to several spectroscopic¹⁻³ and mass spectrometric⁴ investigations. As a part of our ongoing research program for the thermodynamic study of uracil⁵ and other pyrimidine bases, the vapour pressure and the thermodynamic functions of 6-methyluracil have been determined. The vapour pressure measurements of this compound were carried out by using the torsion effusion method. The discussion and the assignment of the infrared gas phase spectrum of 6-methyluracil are also reported.

Experimental

The sample was kindly supplied by the Hungarian Academy of Sciences and purified by recrystallizing from water and then it was sublimated under vacuum. A check of its purity was made by measuring the melting point of the sample $594 \pm 1 \text{ K}$ ($593 \pm 1 \text{ K}$).⁶

(A) Vapour Pressure measurements :

The basis of the method is well known^{7,8} when the sample, contained in a graphite cell and suspended by means of a tungsten wire in the isothermal region of the furnace, is heated under vacuum, the vapour pressure is derived by the measure of the torsion angle α of the cell through the relation :

$$P = 2K\alpha / (a_1 l_1 f_1 + a_2 l_2 f_2)$$

where K is the constant of the torsion wire (30 in diameter and 35 cm in length); a_1 and a_2 are the areas of the effusion holes, l_1 and l_2 are the respective distances from the rotation axis and f_1 and f_2 the corresponding geometrical correction factors. In this study the correction factors are derived from

the equation⁹ $1/f = 0.0147(R/r)^2 + 0.3490(R/r) + 0.9982$ where r and R are the radius and the thickness of the effusion hole respectively. The temperature of the cell was measured by a calibrated chromel-alumel thermocouple inserted in a second cell below the torsion crucible. In order to test the thermodynamic equilibrium existing within the used cell and the reliability of the temperature measurements, the sulphur vapour pressure was determined in the temperature range 390-510 K and the obtained data were compared with the selected ones reported by Hultgreen¹⁰.

The vapour pressure of 6-methyluracil determined in two runs over the temperature range 426-503 K are reported in Table 1 and plotted in Fig. 1. The straight line $\lg P$ against $1/T$ obtained by least square treatment of the experimental data is given

Fig. 1. Vapour pressure experimental values of 6-methyluracil.

TABLE 1—VAPOUR PRESSURE DETERMINED BY TORSION-EFFUSION METHOD

T (k)	number of points	α^a (degree)	P (kPa)	$-\Delta[(G_T^0 - H_{T,0}^0)/T]$ (J/K mol)	$\Delta H_{T,0}^0$ (kJ/mol)
Run 1					
426	1	2	3.53 10^{-4}	200.7	130.0
433	1	3	5.29 „	200.7	130.6
439	1	5	8.83 „	200.6	130.6
443	1	7	1.26 10^{-3}	200.5	130.4
455	1	17	3.00 „	200.4	130.6
461	1	26	4.59 „	200.4	130.7
469	2	38	6.71 „	200.3	131.0
470	6	49	8.65 „	200.3	130.7
472	5	60	1.06 10^{-2}	200.3	130.4
473	3	64	1.13 „	200.3	130.5
474	2	69	1.53 „	200.3	130.5
475	3	73	1.29 „	200.3	130.5
476	2	80	1.41 „	200.2	130.4
479	3	90	1.59 „	200.2	130.7
480	3	105	1.85 „	200.2	130.4
482	1	125	1.98 „	200.2	130.2
483	3	130	2.30 „	200.2	130.3
484	2	135	2.38 „	200.2	130.5
486	2	130	2.30 „	200.1	131.1
488	2	170	3.00 „	200.1	130.6
489	3	173	3.06 „	200.1	130.8
491	3	209	3.69 „	200.1	130.5
492	3	216	3.81 „	200.1	130.6
493	3	250	4.41 „	200.1	130.3
495	2	278	4.91 „	200.0	130.4
498	2	300	5.30 „	200.0	130.8
499	3	330	5.82 „	200.0	130.7
501	1	345	6.09 „	200.0	131.0
503	1	404	7.13 „	200.0	130.9
Average					130.6 \pm 0.2 ^b
Run 2					
427	2	2	3.53 10^{-4}	200.7	130.3
438	1	4	7.06 „	200.6	131.1
449	1	10	3.55 10^{-3}	200.5	130.9
453	3	15	2.65 „	200.5	130.5
463	1	29	5.12 „	200.4	130.9
465	2	33	5.82 „	200.3	130.9
472	2	53	9.35 „	200.3	130.9
473	1	53	1.02 10^{-3}	200.3	130.9
475	1	67	1.18 „	200.2	130.8
477	3	83	1.46 „	200.2	130.5
482	5	112	1.98 „	200.2	130.4
485	2	140	2.47 „	200.1	130.6
487	5	153	2.70 „	200.1	130.7
490	1	190	3.36 „	200.1	130.6
494	1	271	4.79 „	200.1	130.2
500	1	334	5.90 „	200.0	130.0
Average					130.7 \pm 0.2 ^b

^aAverage value of the number of points listed in the second law.
^bThe error is the standard deviation.

by the following equation :

$$\lg P(\text{kPa}) = 12.09 \pm 0.07 - (6652 \pm 34)/T$$

where the associated errors are the standard deviations.

(B) Spectroscopic Study :

The experimental apparatus is that described in details in previous works^{11,12}. The infrared spectra of gaseous 6-methyluracil were recorded over the frequency range 100-4000 cm^{-1} with a Perkin-Elmer

180 IR grating spectrophotometer purged with dry nitrogen. Stainless steel cells, 30 cm pathlength, were used. Temperature of the cell was kept around 470 K during the scanning of the spectrum and measured with iron to constantan thermocouple. Nitrogen gas at one atm. was used as diffusion barrier. Temperature was recycled during the experimental runs as a tool of distinguishing among the spectra due to the desired species and the background.

The assignment of thirty-nine normal vibrations was performed comparing the infrared gas phase spectrum of 6-methyluracil with that of gaseous uracil³ and taking into account the results of a quantum chemical study at CNDO/2 level on the electronic structure of some uracil derivatives¹³. The conclusion of previous vibrational investigations on uracil and some pyrimidine bases^{1,2} were also considered in the present assignment. The infrared spectrum of 6-methyluracil can be regarded as the overlap of the vibrations belonging to uracil with the modes of the methyl group. The analysis of the spectrum suggest that our expectations are plentifully fulfilled. In this paper we discuss the characteristic features only for sake of brevity since a detailed study on gaseous and matrix isolated uracil will be reported elsewhere³.

The NH stretching vibrations are attributed to the bands observed at 3415 and 3435 cm^{-1} which positions are in agreement with the calculations performed by Harsanyi *et al*¹³ for uracil. The absorption at 3040 cm^{-1} is readily assigned to the νCH stretching while the peaks between 2970 and 2985 cm^{-1} are confidently attributed to the methyl stretching modes.

Both the theoretical calculation¹³ and the conclusions of the previous works^{1,2} support the identification of the νCO , νCC and νCN stretchings. As regards the νCO motions, the two expected vibrations are recognized in the strong doublet at 1711 and 1724 cm^{-1} while the line at 1620 cm^{-1} can be reasonably related to the νCC vibration. In the region 1300-1480 cm^{-1} three additional bands falling at 1390, 1444 and 1460 cm^{-1} are observed. These absorptions are not present in the gaseous spectrum of uracil and their number and position suggest that they could belong to the methyl deformations. The same argumentations can be reliably employed in the assignment of the bands lying at 955, 660 and 520 cm^{-1} and attributed to the $\nu\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ stretching and to the in-plane and out-of-plane $\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ deformations. At last, the absorption observed at 1030 cm^{-1} seems most probably due to the methyl rocking mode.

The vibrational analysis foresees three out-of-plane ring torsions. Two of them are assigned to the bands occurring at 127 and 350 cm^{-1} on the

basis of the theoretic expectations¹³ which also indicate that the remaining torsion should be expected below 100 cm⁻¹, therefore out of the range of our investigation. The proposed assignment is reported in Table 2.

TABLE 2—GAS PHASE IR SPECTRUM OF 6-METHYLURACIL AND BANDS ASSIGNMENT

Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	Assignment
3435	NH stretching
3415	" "
3040	CH stretching
2985	methyl stretching
2980	" "
2970	" "
1724	CO stretching
1711	" "
1620	CC stretching
1480	NH deformation
1460	methyl deformation
1444	" "
1415	CN stretching
1390	methyl deformation
1366	NH deformation
1321	NH deformation
1265	CN stretching
1155	CH deformation
1058	CN stretching
1030	methyl rocking
1015	skeletal deformation
955	C—CH ₃ stretching
940	CN stretching
920	CH out-of-plane deformation
820	CO out-of-plane deformation
744	CJ stretching
731	CO out-of-plane deformation
700	CH out-of-plane deformation
660	C—CH ₃ in-plane deformation
588	skeletal deformation
550	" "
533	CO in-plane deformation
520	C—CH ₃ out-of-plane deformation
477	NH out-of-plane deformation
460	" "
380	CO in-plane deformation
350	out-of-plane torsion
127	out-of-plane torsion
67 ^a	out-of-plane torsion

^a This frequency is one of the out-of-plane torsions calculated by Császár and Harsányi for uracil (see paragraph B, ref. 1³)

(C) Thermodynamic Functions :

In Table 3 the thermodynamic functions of gaseous 6-methyluracil are listed. In order to calculate these functions, the results of the present spectroscopic study are employed to derive the vibrational contribution to the partition function. Bond distances and angles are estimated as follows since no structural data are at present available : the same geometrical parameters of uracil¹⁴ are assumed to hold for 6-methyluracil while the C—CH₃ and the CH distances are kept equal to 1.53 and 1.11 Å respectively ; the HCH angles of the methyl group are supposed to be tetrahedral. The electronic ground state is taken as ¹Σ and the contribution to the electronic partition functions reported in this

paper are carried out through the usual statistical method¹⁶.

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF GASEOUS 6-METHYLURACIL

T (K)	S _T ^o (J/mol K)	-(G _T ^o - H ₂₉₈ ^o)/T (J/mol K)	(H _T ^o - H ₂₉₈ ^o) (kJ/mol)
298.15	339.3	339.3	0.00
300	340.0	339.5	0.15
350	356.7	340.9	5.50
400	373.3	342.2	12.40
450	389.1	345.6	19.60
500	406.0	350.3	27.85
550	420.5	355.2	35.90
600	435.6	361.1	44.70

Conclusion

The vapour pressure of 6-methyluracil determined from torsion effusion measurements permitted to evaluate the second law sublimation $\Delta H_{465}^o = 127 \pm 0.6$ kJ/mol. At each temperature a value of the third law sublimation ΔH_{298}^o was calculated and reported in Table 1, the necessary free energy functions of solid 6-methyluracil were estimated through the heat capacity values of solid uracil⁵ corrected for the difference $C_p^o(\text{CH}_3) - C_p^o(\text{H})^{17}$, those of the gaseous species are determined experimentally (section C). The average third law $\Delta H_{298}^o = 130.6 \pm 0.2$ kJ/mol (the error is standard deviation) coincides with that derived from the second law $\Delta H_{298}^o = 130.7 \pm 0.6$ kJ/mol corrected at 298.15 K using the heat content difference ($H_{465}^o - H_{298}^o$). The heat content of the solid phase was calculated through the estimated C_p^o values and those of the gas phase were derived by the $H_T^o - H_{298}^o$ reported in Table 3.

Even if the agreement between second and third law ΔH_{298}^o value is excellent, we believe that the associated error should be about 6 kJ/mol taking into account the uncertainties associated to the temperature measurements, to the calibration factors and to thermodynamic functions estimation of 6-methyluracil (s). So that the value $\Delta H_{298}^o = 131 \pm 7$ kJ/mol associated to the vaporization process of 6-methyluracil is proposed.

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